

A Note on the Bleaching of Shellac.

BY

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The bleaching of shellac, as described in Rogers and Aubert's "Industrial Chemistry," 1912, p. 701, is effected by sodium hypochlorite in a hot alkaline solution of the shellac. In the same place it is stated that a peculiarity of bleached shellac is its gradual change into a modification insoluble in alcohol and alkalis, which change inevitably takes place in time with every bleached shellac. The change is said to be favoured by high temperatures.

Gadre describes the bleaching of shellac (*Chem. News*, 1921, 123, 127), the process being essentially the same as described by Rogers and Aubert. He gives figures showing that a sample which was almost completely soluble in alcohol when freshly made was soluble only to the extent of 56.6 per cent. after exposure to light and air for 6 months. Also he analysed an old sample of English make and found it was soluble only to the extent of 12.1 per cent.

Rogers and Aubert prescribe the preparation of a solution of sodium hypochlorite, (from 10 kg. bleaching powder for every 10 kg. shellac) and direct that it should be added to the hot alkaline solution of the shellac until the latter becomes wine-yellow in colour. They

do not state how much of this solution is generally required. Gadre used the whole of the hypochlorite solution obtained from 1 part of bleaching powder for the bleaching of 1 part of shellac.

The present authors have bleached shellac by Rogers and Aubert's process, taking care to use the minimum quantity of hypochlorite solution necessary to bleach the material. For an ordinary Indian bazaar sample of shellac the hypochlorite solution from 1 part of bleaching powder sufficed to bleach 6.5 parts of shellac. The alkaline solution was then cooled and acidified, without allowing the temperature to rise, when the shellac was precipitated as a granular solid which was collected, washed very thoroughly, suspended in water and treated with 1 part of sodium thiosulphate solution (10 per cent.) for each part of shellac. The shellac was collected, washed very thoroughly and air-dried. Samples of bleached shellac so produced have remained for the most part soluble in alcohol for over 3 years. The air-dried powder was kept in ordinary stoppered bottles in Cawnpore.

Sample prepared in February 1923; analysed April 1926.

Insoluble in alcohol	...	9.5 per cent.
Ash	...	nil.

Sample prepared in November 1924; analysed April 1926.

Insoluble in alcohol	...	1.1 per cent.
Ash	...	0.5 „ „

We therefore claim that if the minimum quantity of hypochlorite is used for bleaching and the bleached product is precipitated in granular form, washed very thoroughly and treated with sodium thiosulphate to remove any absorbed chlorine, bleached shellac can be

prepared which will remain for the the most part soluble in alcohol for years.

In the course of these experiments it was noticed that it was difficult to remove all acid from the precipitated shellac. The moist shellac pressed against litmus paper turned it red when the wash-water was neutral to litmus.

It was also noticed in the bleaching of specially dark lac, recovered from lac-dye, that it was necessary in bleaching to use solutions containing the minimum quantity of alkali. Under these conditions the hypochlorite exerted its maximum bleaching effect. If a larger quantity of alkali was used the bleaching was not so good and the bleached shellac was softer (melted at a lower temperature) than the original material. Probably the same would be the case in the bleaching of ordinary shellac.

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Received May 4, 1926.